

Students' Perception on the Indonesianization of College Slogans as an Effort to Dignify the Indonesian Language

Sri Nur Yuliyawati¹, Hazma², Krisna Yudha Bakhti³

¹(Department of Civil Engineering, Politeknik Negeri Bandung, Indonesia)

²(Department of Accounting, Politeknik Negeri Bandung, Indonesia)

³(Department of English, Politeknik Negeri Bandung, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: This study investigates the students' perception on the Indonesianization of college slogans as an effort to dignify the Indonesian Language. This study is aimed to (1) identify the language used in college slogans; (2) describe students' perception on college slogans written in foreign languages, (3) formulate the equal translation of the foreign language slogans, and (4) describe students' acceptance on the translation of foreign language slogans. This study shows that 1) seven slogans are written in the Indonesian language, 11 slogans are written in foreign languages, and 2 slogans are written in local languages; 2) 53% of college students choose slogans written in foreign language as their college slogans. Choosing foreign language slogans means that the students are fairly loyal, proud, and aware of the language norms; 3) 47% of students choose to translate foreign language slogans into Indonesian language and 53% of students prefer to use foreign language slogans and they also think that translating foreign language slogans into the Indonesian language is not necessary. This situation indicates that the students are fairly loyal, proud, and aware of the language norms.

KEYWORDS—College slogans, Indonesianization, Indonesian language, language dignity, students' perception

I. INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian language has begun to be shifted. The use of foreign language has been found in more than 20,000 business naming in public places in 27 regencies/cities in West Java Province, Indonesia [1]. Besides, the use of foreign languages in public spaces in several cities in Indonesia has increasingly widespread. This fact is contrary to the Law Number 24 the Year 2009 Article 38 Paragraph 1 about Flags, Languages, and Symbol of Countries as well as the National Anthem which states that the Indonesian language must be used in public signs, directions, public facilities, banners, and other information tools.

The uses of foreign languages are also found in college slogans in Indonesia, for example Padjadjaran University with "World Class University", Institut Pertanian Bogor with "Searching and Serving The Best", Institut Teknologi Bandung with "In Harmonia Progressio", Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta with "The Leading in Character Education", Politeknik Negeri Bandung with "Assuring Your Future", and other colleges also use foreign languages in their slogans. Those slogans are certainly published and socialized in banners, nameplates, and others in public spaces. The use of language in public spaces reflects how a society's attitude towards its language. Maryani in [2] stated that when a good and correct Indonesian language is used in public spaces, it reflects the society's positive attitude towards the Indonesian language. Conversely, when foreign languages are used in public spaces, it shows the society's negative attitude towards the Indonesian language.

The trends of using foreign languages in college slogans have been followed by other parties. They use this condition as reference for naming their business. When this trend occurs frequently and uncontrollably, the use of foreign language slogans will be overflowed in public spaces. This may cause a shift in the position of the Indonesian language as the state language. In several studies, it is explained that French is displaced by English

in Montreal, Tiwa language of the Indian tribe is displaced by Spanish, and then Spanish is displaced by English [3].

The language shift certainly does not want to happen in Indonesia. The Indonesian language as one of national identity needs to be maintained and strengthened to show the existence of Indonesia to the world. Strengthening the nation's identity with the Indonesian language requires participation and support by upholding the national unity and positive attitude towards the Indonesian language [4]. Asnan [5] also stated that one way to maintain Indonesian identity as a national identity is to use the Indonesian language in public spaces. Moreover, Suhendar, the Head of the National Agency for Language Development and Cultivation, urges all parties to prioritize the use of the Indonesian language in public spaces to protect the state language dignity [6].

Research topics on slogans are quite common. A study on the antecedents of slogan liking revealed that the liking for a slogan may be unrelated to media expenditure, and driven largely by the clarity of the message, the exposition of the benefits, rhymes, and creativity. Further, in sharp contrast to industry practice and conventional belief, the study finds that jingles or brevity have no systematic effects on the likeability of slogans [7]. Another study on 15 slogans of District Gujrat Schools described the semantic perspective of these slogans. From this analysis, it was found that hyperbole is frequently used in slogans. In addition, short sentences, inspiring and motivational words are also used since they are an effective way to advertise [8]. A study on the effect of difficult English slogans versus easy English slogans in product advertisements on evaluations extending beyond text evaluation was also conducted. The findings showed that the easy English slogans were evaluated better than the difficult English slogans and generally resulted in a better attitude toward the ads and toward the product and in a higher purchase intention. Thus, difficult-to-understand foreign-language slogans were found to have negative effects on ad effectiveness, which extended beyond text evaluation [9]. The frequent use of English in international advertising and people's preference for English versus local languages was investigated. The result showed that the Dutch prefer and appreciate the use of English slogans as it is easier to understand. When it is too difficult, they prefer to have the Dutch equivalent [10]. A study on the use of French as a foreign language in Dutch publicity campaigns showed that there was no conclusive evidence found for the effectiveness of foreign language uses in advertising [11]. From those studies, it is concluded that research topics on slogans have been conducted. However, a study on the use of foreign languages in college slogans and its relation to dignify the Indonesian language are not found. Thus, conducting this study is novel. This study is expected to contribute to the efforts of dignifying the Indonesian language through the use of the Indonesian language in college slogans.

Based on the problems stated previously, this study is aimed to (1) identify the language used in college slogans; (2) describe students' perception on college slogans written in foreign languages, (3) formulate the equal translation of the foreign language slogans, and (4) describe students' acceptance on the translation of foreign language slogans.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Slogans

In Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI), or Indonesian Dictionary, slogan / slo-gan /n 1 is an interesting or striking and easy to remember words or short sentences to tell something; 2 words or short sentences that are interesting, striking, and easy to remember to explain the purpose of an ideology of a group, organization, political party, and so on. Based on these definitions, the characteristics of slogan are concise, interesting, and easy to remember; presented in the form of phrases, clauses, or sentences; it contains the ideology of an organization or community.

A slogan is one of the most important elements in business because it can contribute to the success of an advertisement, its products, and even its brand. In today's business market, effective slogans should be easy to remember and provide an accurate description of a company or institution, especially when they reveal prices, services, or consumers' expectations. In some cases, a slogan can convey messages that the company wants to communicate, for example, the slogan of a cosmetic company that invites a change through the slogan "Because you're worth it", or a shoes-company that encourages customers to achieve their goals through the slogan "just

do it". These slogans build a brand identity that distinguishes one company from another, attracting customers who want to feel the benefits of the brand [12].

A slogan can be intended to influence, encourage, and motivate the community. Generally, the purpose of making a slogan is to convey information which must be formulated in short sentences, but the message or information can be understood easily by the public. A slogan is not only a tagline created by the advertisement makers but it plays a strategic role because it can influence the customer's mind so that it makes the customer believe that the product being advertised is reliable. A study entitled *The Meaning of Slogan in a Truck: Semiotic Analysis of the Roland Barthes Model* concluded that slogan language is a message of hope, a form of rejection, a moral message, a representation of life, and self-expression [13]. These meanings are very useful for people who can take a positive angle from the meaning itself.

Based on its purposes, a slogan is divided into several types, they are health slogans, educational slogans, hygiene slogans, environmental slogans, and so on. Educational slogans are usually found in educational environments such as schools [14]. Having a slogan is a necessity of an institution. It is explained that a slogan has an important substance that is the repeated expression of an idea. It is often equated with the promotion of a product or service because the message about the product, services, or basic matters that represent the contents of the message can be delivered to attract the attention of the intended audiences [15]. It also can be used to explain a concept of an organization or institution and to build public perception so that the existence of the slogan can be a reminder of an institution.

To socialize/market the philosophy that underlies the idea of academic development and/or higher education services, colleges usually make a slogan which is sometimes adjusted to the vision, mission, and goals of the college [16].

2.2 Dignifying the Indonesian Language

At present, the effort to dignify the Indonesian language is intensively carried out by Indonesian language enthusiasts. The background of this effort is the use of foreign languages in public spaces. Based on the studies in 27 cities and regencies in Indonesia, 70% of public spaces have been overflowed by foreign languages, especially public spaces that are managed by private sectors so that the Indonesian language which should exist in the public spaces in Indonesia becomes undignified. Indonesian language dignity is a process/effort to re-dignify the state language [17]. Meanwhile, Garvin and Mathiot [18] stated the dignity of the language contains at least three main characteristics they are language loyalty, language pride, and awareness of language norms. Language loyalty is an attitude that encourages people to maintain language independence. Language pride is an attitude that encourages people or groups to make their language a personal or group identity. While, awareness of language norms is an attitude that encourages the use of language carefully, correctively, politely, and appropriately.

As a State Language, Indonesian language functions as:

1. the official language;
2. medium of instruction in education;
3. medium for communication at the national level for planning and development purposes;
4. medium for cultural, scientific, and technological development. [19]

In line with the four functions of the Indonesian language, the government of Indonesia has regulated the use of the Indonesian language through Law No. 24 the Year 2009 concerning Flags, Languages, and Symbols of the country, as well as the National Anthem. Regarding the use of language, the Indonesian language must be used as the official language of the country, medium of instruction in education, medium of communication at the national level, development of national culture, trade transaction and documentation, as well as medium for developing and applying science, technology, art, and mass media languages.

The use of foreign language in official meetings, mass media, and public places is now showing changes in the community language behavior. The Indonesian language should not dissolve in the flow of global communication using foreign languages. If it is not managed well, the identity of Indonesia as a nation may

fade, and it might be threatened to dissolve in the flow of global culture so that there is a shift in the position of the Indonesian language as the state language. This condition is in line with a statement “The amount and speed of movement towards the extinction of languages in the world and also in Indonesia is not only a linguistic disaster but also information about socio-economics that is closely related to remoteness, powerlessness ...”[20].

Language shifts can occur due to several things, they are bilingualism that dominates the use of new languages compared to existing languages and the socio-economic conditions of language-speaking communities that identify themselves to new languages [3]. To anticipate the language shift in Indonesia, the Head of National Agency for Language Development and the Cultivation Republic of Indonesia, with letter number 5947/G/BS/2016 dated August 8 the Year 2016, expects all parties to commit to dignify the Indonesian language in the society and nation life so that the Indonesian language can truly become an image, identity, and symbol of national sovereignty.

Various efforts to dignify the Indonesian language have been carried out, that is by legalizing Law No. 24 the Year 2009 concerning language, the cooperation of language bodies with local governments and private institutions to socialize the language law, the Indonesian language curriculum for elementary and secondary schools conceptualized by the Language Board, and so on. The efforts to dignify the Indonesian language can be carried out by Indonesian citizens in various ways. One of them is through translation [21].

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data

This study applied a descriptive method to describe the data. The data was the slogans of 20 colleges in West Java province in Indonesia, students' perceptions on the use of foreign language slogans, students' acceptance on the Indonesian translation of foreign language slogans. The determination of 20 colleges is based on the four-part of the region in West Java; western region, eastern region, northern region, and central region. From the western region, it is represented by 4 colleges in Bogor; Institut Pertanian Bogor, Universitas Pakuan Bogor, Universitas Ibnu Khaldun Bogor, and Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Bogor. From the eastern region, it is represented by 5 colleges in Garut; Sekolah Tinggi Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan (STKIP) Garut, Sekolah Tinggi Teknologi Garut, Universitas Garut, Akademi Manajemen dan Ilmu Komputer (AMIK) Garut, and Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi (STIE) Yasa Anggana. From the northern region, it is represented by 5 colleges in Cirebon and Indramayu; Universitas Swadaya Gunung Jati (UNSWAGATI), Universitas Wiralodra (UNWIR), Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 (UNTAG), Universitas Muhammadiyah Cirebon (UMC), dan Politeknik Negeri Indramayu. From the central region, it is represented by 6 colleges in Bandung: Universitas Katolik Parayangan, Universitas Pasundan, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Telkom University, Institut Teknologi Bandung, and Politeknik Negeri Bandung. In addition, this determination is also based on the types of college, they are universities, institutes, polytechnics, and academy.

3.2 Data Collection Method

To obtain relevant data, interviews, literature review, and questionnaires were applied. Interviews were conducted to obtain information about the Indonesian language dignity and the formulation of college slogans. Literature review was used to obtain the slogans used by 20 colleges and to obtain information students' perceptions on the use of foreign language slogans and their acceptance on the Indonesian translation of the foreign language slogans.

3.3 Flow of the Study

The study was started with a literature analysis on language dignity, the identification of dignified Indonesian language characters, and college slogans. Literature analysis on language dignity and slogans focused on the results of studies on Indonesian language dignity, the implementation of Indonesian language dignity, community's attitudes towards Indonesian language dignity, the results of studies on slogans, and the formulation of Indonesian slogans. Although it was conducted at the beginning of the study, literature analysis on language dignity and slogans was carried out continuously until the very last step.

From the results of the studies on language dignity and college slogans, an instrument in the form of questions was created as a guideline to identify the slogan used by colleges in the West Java province and instruments for translating the foreign language slogans. After the data was collected and described, translating foreign language slogans into Indonesian language were conducted. The next step was developing and distributing questionnaires to obtain data of the students' perceptions on the use of foreign language slogan and their acceptance on the Indonesian translation of the foreign language slogans.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Description of College Slogans in West Java

From the literature analysis of 20 college slogans, it is obtained that 11 college slogans are written in foreign languages (9 slogans are in English and 2 slogans are in Latin), 7 slogans are written in the Indonesian language, 1 slogan in Sundanese language (local language of West Java province), and 1 slogan is in the Javanese language. Table 1 below shows the use of language in college slogans.

TABLE 1 the use of language in College Slogans

Name of College	Slogan	Language
Politeknik Negeri Bandung	<i>Assuring your Future</i>	English
Institut Teknologi Bandung	<i>In Harmonia Progressio (Progress in Harmony)</i>	Latin
Telkom University	<i>Creating the Future</i>	English
Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia	<i>A Leading and Outstanding University</i>	English
Universitas Pasundan	<i>Pengkuh Agamana, Luhung Elmuna, Jembar Budayana</i>	Sundanese
Universitas Katolik Parahyangan	<i>Bakuning Hyang Mrih Guna Santyaya Bhakti</i>	Javanese
Institut Pertanian Bogor	<i>Searching and Serving the Best</i>	English
Universitas pakuan Bogor	Unggul, Madiri, dan Berkarakter	Indonesian
Universitas Ibnu Khaldun Bogor	<i>Toward Leading Islamic University</i>	English
Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Bogor	<i>Dum Vivimus Servimus (Life Dedicated to the Service)</i>	Latin
Sekolah Tinggi Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan Garut	Ilmiah, Religius, Berkualitas	Indonesian
Sekolah Tinggi Teknologi Garut	<i>The Spirit of Technology</i>	English
Universitas Garut	Iman, Ilmu, Amal	Indonesian
Akademi Manajemen dan Ilmu Komputer Garut	<i>The Smart Campus - We shared Information Technology-Based Computer</i>	English
Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi) Yasa Anggana	Kami Memahami Masa Depan Pendidikan Anda	Indonesian
Universitas Swadaya Gunung Jati	Unggulan, Kompetitif, Mandiri	Indonesian
Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Cirebon	<i>Entrepreneurship University</i>	English
Politeknik Negeri Indramayu	<i>Industrial Based Education</i>	English
Universitas Wiralodra	Unggul dan Kompetitif	Indonesian
Universitas Muhammadiyah Cirebon	Islami, Profesional, Mandiri	Indonesian

4.2 Students' Perception on the Use of Foreign Language Slogans

From the questionnaire, there are 53% of students choose foreign language slogans. This means that the students are fairly loyal, proud, and aware of the language norms in the foreign language slogan. The percentage of students' perception of the use of foreign language slogans can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Percentage of students' perception of the use of Language in their college slogans

The questionnaire shows the college students responses on the reasons for maintaining the English slogans. They are summarized below.

- a. English is more interesting, cool, and classy.
- b. English makes the students confident and increases their motivation.
- c. English is considered more modern, professional, and interesting.
- d. English can make their college more attractive.
- e. English is an international language so that people will be amazed.
- f. English slogans seem more impressive.
- g. The use of English slogans is beneficial in any fields.
- h. The English slogan motivates the students to study and speak English.
- i. The use of English slogan is a way to global competition.
- j. English is an international language.
- k. English slogan makes their collage more outstanding.
- l. English is a global language.
- m. English is more competitive than any other language.
- n. English is an international language which can be understood by many people.
- o. English can make their campus popular at both national and international levels.
- p. Every people understand the English slogan.
- q. English slogan is essential to attract foreign students.
- r. English is understood by other countries and it can show that our campus is at a higher level.
- s. English is important to survive in the international competition.
- t. It is important to promote our campus to other countries.

From the reasons written by the students, it concludes that they are more confident using English to express themselves (implied in a, b, c, d, e, and f). Likewise, for academic development, the students choose English because it is more appropriate to use (implied in g, h, i, j, k, and l). They also assess that English will help their college to compete internationally so that they are known and chosen by the international community (implied in m, n, o, p, q, r, s, and t).

4.3 The Indonesianization of Foreign Language Slogans as an effort to Indonesian Language Dignity

A good slogan must be easily understood and remembered by people. This has not been fulfilled because college slogans are mostly written in foreign languages. The foreign-language slogans are not easy to be understood by most Indonesian people because English is a foreign language. To make them easily understand and remember, the college slogans in Indonesia should be written in the Indonesian language. This is in line with what is stated in Law No. 24 the Year 2009, a slogan must prioritize the use of state language of the country, but it may be accompanied by local or foreign languages. For that reason, one of the efforts to dignify the Indonesian language is through translation [21]. Table 2 lists the Indonesianization or

Indonesian translation of foreign language slogans.

Table 2 the Indonesianization of Foreign Language Slogans

Name of College	Slogans	Equal translation in the Indonesian language
Politeknik Negeri Bandung	<i>Assuring your Future</i>	Jaminan Masa Depan
Institut Teknologi Bandung	<i>In Harmonia Progressio (Progress in Harmony)</i>	Maju dalam Harmoni
Telkom University	<i>Creating the Future</i>	Menciptakan Masa Depan
Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia	<i>A Leading and Outstanding University</i>	Universitas Pelopor dan Unggul
Universitas Pasundan	<i>Pengkuh Agamana, Luhung Elmuna, Jembar Budayana.</i>	
Universitas Katolik Parahyangan	<i>Bakuning Hyang Mrih Guna Santyaya Bhakti</i>	
Institut Pertanian Bogor	<i>Searching and Serving the Best</i>	Mencari dan Melayani yang Terbaik
Universitas pakuan Bogor	Unggul, Madiri, dan Berkarakter	
Universitas Ibnu Khaldun Bogor	<i>Toward Leading Islamic University</i>	Menuju Universitas Islam yang Terdepan
Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Bogor	<i>Dum Vivimus Servimus (Life Dedicated to the Service)</i>	Dedikasikan Hidup untuk Pelayanan
Sekolah Tinggi Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan Garut	Ilmiah, Religius, Berkualitas	
Sekolah Tinggi Teknologi Garut	<i>The Spirit of Technology</i>	Semangat Teknologi
Universitas Garut	<i>Iman, Ilmu, Amal</i>	
Akademi Manajemen dan Ilmu Komputer Garut	<i>The Smart Campus - We shared Information Technology Based Computer.</i>	Kampus cerdas- Kami berbagi Komputer Berbasis Teknologi Informasi.
Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Yasa Anggana	<i>Kami Memahami Masa Depan Pendidikan Anda</i>	
Universitas Swadaya Gunung Jati	<i>Unggulan, Kompetitif, Mandiri</i>	
Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Cirebon	<i>Entrepreneurship University</i>	Universitas Kewirausahaan
Politeknik Negeri Indramayu	<i>Industrial Based Education</i>	Pendidikan Berbasis Industri
Universitas Wiralodra	<i>Unggul dan Kompetitif</i>	
Universitas Muhammadiyah Cirebon	<i>Islami, Profesional, Mandiri”.</i>	

4.4 Students' Acceptance of the Indonesianization of Foreign Language Slogans

From the questionnaire on the students' acceptance of the Indonesianization of foreign language slogans, 47% of students choose to translate the foreign language slogans into the Indonesian language. On the other hand, 53% of students prefer to keep foreign language slogans and it is not necessary to translate it into the Indonesian language. This means that the students are fairly loyal, proud, and aware of the language norms in the Indonesian language slogans. The percentage of Students' acceptance of the Indonesianization of foreign language slogans can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure2 the percentage of students' acceptance of the indonesianization of foreign language slogans

The reasons for translating foreign language slogans into the Indonesian language are summarized below.

- a. The Indonesian language is more easily understood and prevent misunderstanding
- b. The use of the Indonesian language can improve social behavior of Indonesian people.
- c. Not all Indonesian understand English.
- d. The use Indonesian language is important to deliver the message in the slogan.
- e. Indonesian language is more important than any other languages.
- f. The Indonesian language is the key to communicate with other people in Indonesia.
- g. The Indonesian language is a national language.
- h. It is an effort to make Indonesian Language an international language.
- i. The Indonesian language has become one of the international languages.
- j. It is an effort to use the Indonesian language in other countries,
- k. The use of the Indonesian language can make it equal to other languages.
- l. It is important to develop Indonesian' awareness on maintaining the Indonesian language so that it will not be shifted by other languages.
- m. The Indonesian language is good so that it can show the Indonesian's pride.
- n. The students love to use their language and culture.
- o. The Indonesian language is part of Sumpah Pemuda (Youth Pledge)
- p. Their colleges are located in Indonesia so that the students must support the use of the Indonesian language.
- q. The use of Indonesian language can increase patriotism to the students.
- r. Indonesia must show its identity so that the Indonesian language must be used.
- s. Indonesia was colonized so that do not let us being colonized by the use of foreign language.
- t. Using the Indonesian language means appreciating the nation's heroes.

From the reasons above, it indicates that the students are confident that the Indonesian language is an easy language to use in various types of communication (implied in statements a, b, c, d, e, f, and g) and they are optimistic that the Indonesian language can be used in international relations (implied by statements h, i, j, and k). In addition, other reasons show that the students have a high sense of nationalism which is expressed using Indonesian language (implied in the statement l to the statement t).

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis, it is found that 1) there are 11 foreign language slogans used by 11 colleges in West Java (9 slogans are written in English and 2 slogans are written in the Latin language); 2) 53% of students choose foreign language in their college slogan. This means that the students are fairly loyal, proud, and aware of the language norms in the use of foreign language slogan. Some reasons are because English is the international language which is understood by people around the world, using English slogans is important to promote their college to other countries, and English slogan can motivate the students to improve their English; 3) Referring to the Law No. 24 the Year 2009, the college slogans must be written in the Indonesian language to dignify the Indonesian language as a state language. Thus, it is required to translate the foreign language slogans into the Indonesian language; 4) 47% of students prefer to translate the foreign language slogans into Indonesian language and 53% of students prefer to use foreign language slogan and it is not necessary to translate it into the Indonesian language. This indicates that the students are fairly loyal, proud, and aware of the language norms in the Indonesian language slogans. The reasons to change foreign language slogans into the Indonesian language are the Indonesian language is used and understood by all Indonesian, Indonesian language is the identity of Indonesia so that they feel proud when using the Indonesian language, and the use of Indonesian language can improve the students' nationalism and patriotism.

VI. Acknowledgments

This article is written based on the result of Applied Research funded by Politeknik Negeri Bandung through The Centre for Research and Community Services.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. N. Dewi, "Ruang Publik Sudah Dijajah Bahasa Asing," 2016. <https://www.pikiran-rakyat.com/pendidikan/pr-01267980/ruang-publik-sudah-dijajah-bahasa-asing-385315>.
- [2] E. Maharani, "Penggunaan Bahasa Asing di Ruang Publik Akan Dibatasi," 2015. <https://nasional.republika.co.id/berita/npqx1x/penggunaan-bahasa-asing-di-ruang-publik-akan-dibatasi>.
- [3] Sumarsono, *Sosiolinguistik*. Yogyakarta: Sabda, 2014.
- [4] U. Solikhah, "BAHASA INDONESIA DALAM INFORMASI DAN IKLAN DI RUANG PUBLIK KOTA PANGKALPINANG," *Sirok Bastra*, 2018, doi: 10.37671/sb.v1i2.15.
- [5] V. Faradika, "Membudayakan Bahasa Indonesia di Ruang Publik," 2015. .
- [6] B. Anselmus, "Jaga Martabat Bahasa Indonesia di Ruang Publik," 2016. <https://www.beritasatu.com/kesra/379145/jaga-martabat-bahasa-indonesia-di-ruang-publik>.
- [7] M. Dass, C. Kohli, P. Kumar, and S. Thomas, "A study of the antecedents of slogan liking," *J. Bus. Res.*, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2014.05.004.
- [8] M. Noor, "Advertisement of School Slogans: Semantic Analysis," *Eur. Acad. Res.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 419–433, 2015.
- [9] B. Hendriks, F. van Meurs, and C. Poos, "Effects of Difficult and Easy English Slogans in Advertising for Dutch Consumers," *J. Curr. Issues Res. Advert.*, 2017, doi: 10.1080/10641734.2017.1291384.
- [10] J. Hornikx, F. van Meurs, and A. de Boer, "English or a local language in advertising?: The appreciation of easy and difficult English slogans in the Netherlands," *J. Bus. Commun.*, 2010, doi: 10.1177/0021943610364524.
- [11] C. Bensink, "The Effectiveness of a Foreign Language Slogans in a Cross-Media and a Single Media Publicity Campaign," 2016. [Online]. Available: https://theses.uibn.ru.nl/bitstream/handle/123456789/3028/Bensink%2C_C.M.B._1.pdf?sequence=1.
- [12] C. Kohli, L. Leuthesser, and R. Suri, "Got slogan? Guidelines for creating effective slogans," *Bus. Horiz.*, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2007.05.002.
- [13] A. Rohim, "Makna Bahasa Slogan Pada Bak Truk: Analisis Semiotika Model Roland Barthes," 2017, [Online]. Available: digilib.uinsby.ac.id: http://digilib.uinsby.ac.id/15407.

-
- [14] A. Ibrahim, "Pengertian Slogan dan Contoh-contohnya," 2013. <https://pengertiandefinisi.com/pengertian-slogan-dan-contohnya>.
- [15] A. Muzakki, "Makna Slogan UINSA Surabaya," 2015. <http://arsipuinsa.uinsby.ac.id/index.php/19-uinsa/kolom-akademisi/169-makna-slogan-uinsa-surabaya>.
- [16] D. K. Samosir, "HEGEMONI PENGGUNAAN BAHASA INGGRIS DALAM SLOGAN PERGURUAN TINGGI (ANALISIS WACANA KRITIS FAIRCLOUGH PADA SLOGAN DUA UNIVERSITAS SWASTA DI KOTA BANDUNG)," *J. Sositologi*, 2016, doi: 10.5614/sostek.itbj.2016.15.1.11.
- [17] M. A. Khak, *Strategi Ekspansi Pemertabatan Bahasa Negara Di Ruang Publik (Badan Bahasa Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan)*. Sumedang: PKP2A I LAN, 2018.
- [18] U. Mansur, "Sikap Bahasa dan Pembelajaran Bahasa Indonesia di Perguruan Tinggi," 2018.
- [19] S. N. Yuliyawati, *Bahasa Indonesia untuk Aktivitas Ilmiah*. Bandung: UPT Penerbit Politeknik Negeri Bandung, 2015.
- [20] G. A. Ibrahim, "Bahasa Terancam Punah: Fakta, Sebab-Musabab, Gejala, dan Strategi Perawatannya," *Masy. Linguist. Indones.*, 2011.
- [21] Abu, "Pemertabatan Bahasa Indonesia Melalui Penerjemahan," 2015. <http://www.balaibahasajateng.web.id/index.php/read/home/>.